

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Article

Formulation and evaluation of herbal sunscreen cream.

Vaishnavi P. Bansod^{*1}, Vinayak A. Katekar² and Swati Deshmukh³

¹Department of Pharmacy, Shraddha Institute of Pharmacy, Washim, Maharashtra, India.

²Department of Quality Assurance, Shraddha Institute of Pharmacy, Washim, Maharashtra, India.

³Department of Pharmacology, Shraddha Institute of Pharmacy, Washim, Maharashtra, India.

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 31 July 2024

Accepted: 31 July 2024

Published: 02 Aug 2024

Keywords:

Sunscreen, UV rays
,sunburn,skin,photoprotection

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.13167007

ABSTRACT

Because the harsh synthetic chemicals and pollution of today's fast-paced lifestyle are detrimental to our health, nature has given us its ageless, notable herbal ingredients. In addition to increasing the risk of skin cancer, UV rays are the primary cause of sunburn. Sunscreen is a topical chemical that shields the skin from UV rays by reflecting or partially absorbing them. The study of phytoconstituents entails figuring out how plants work and then applying that understanding to develop novel pharmaceutical products and their formulations. Among its many benefits are its antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, anti-diabetic, and anti-hypertensive qualities. Plants afflicted with oxidative stress-related illnesses will eventually produce potentially therapeutic secondary metabolites. sunscreen is a chemical that shields the skin from the sun's UV rays when exposed to it excessively. Due to its capacity to inhibit UV-induced sunburn (known as the sun protection factor, or SPF), sunscreen is used for sun protection. The goal of the current study is to create sunscreen lotion using extracts from bioactive goods that has a broad spectrum of anti-UV radiation efficiency and a lower concentration of chemical UV filters. The extracts such as Citrus sinensis (Orange peel), Aloe vera (Liliaceae), Carrot oil (Daucus carota), Turmeric (Curcuma Longa).

INTRODUCTION

Sunscreen is a chemical compound that helps shield the skin from ultraviolet light. Sunburn is caused by UV B radiation, however UV A may cause more skin damage. A sunscreen that blocks both wavebands is ideal. The aim of this study was to develop a topical herbal sunscreen formulation with some fixed oils and a mixture of medicinal

herbs. Actinic keratosis, melanoma, and squamous cell carcinoma can all be avoided with regular sunscreen use.[1] Sunscreen chemicals can be either inorganic or organic. Sunscreen products that protect skin from UV radiation by reflecting or absorbing them are also known as sunscreen lotions. The growth in skin cancer instances and the photodamaging effects of UV radiation have

***Corresponding Author:** Vaishnavi P. Bansod

Address: Department of Pharmacy, Shraddha Institute of Pharmacy, Washim, Maharashtra, India.

Email ✉: vaishnavibansod9579@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

led to a surge in the usage of sunblock products, which have shown promising outcomes in symptom reduction. Ingredients in sunscreen should be fully safe, free of chemicals, non-irritating, non-toxic, photostabilized, and capable of protecting skin from the sun.[2] Skin cancer, photoaging, and sunburn are the results of this. Owing to these detrimental effects of UV radiation, sunscreen formulations that boost SPF, cure sunburns and suntans, prevent skin cancer, and slow down skin ageing must be developed. Sunscreen formulation aims to enhance protection against UV range dilation by obstructing them. Flavonoids, phenolic compounds, and herbal oils are essential for UV protection because they possess antioxidant properties and can absorb UV radiation in the UV-A region. Chemicals included in synthetic sunscreens have been linked to dermatitis-like allergic reactions, cell mutation, hormone fluctuations, and DNA damage.[3] Using an aloe vera gel extract can help you physically

protect yourself from the sun. It is gentle for the skin and non-greasy. It contains *Daucus carota* extract. Because it absorbs UVB rays, sunscreens typically incorporate this substance. skin tone uniformity. For this reason, carrot oil may absorb UVB rays. assist in reducing the hyperpigmentation's look. Vitamin C content in citrus sinus powder is very high. Additionally, the synthesis of collagen and elastin enhances the appearance of your skin.[4] You can aid yourself by applying an aloe vera gel extract as a physical sun protection. It is non-greasy and kind to the skin. *Daucus carota* extract is present. This material is commonly seen in sunscreens because it absorbs UVB radiation. consistency of skin tone. Carrot oil may therefore absorb UVB radiation. help to lessen the appearance of hyperpigmentation. Citrus sinus powder has a very high level of vitamin C. The production of elastin and collagen also improves the appearance of your skin.[5]

Ranges of UV rays

Table no .2 Ranges of UV rays

UV A	The wavelength, between 320 and 400 nm, causes immediate sunburn and tanning by destroying the dermis and interior skin cells.
UV B	The wavelength, between 320 and 400 nm, causes immediate sunburn and tanning by destroying the dermis and interior skin cells.
UV C	The shortest wavelength, which is between 100 and 290 nm, causes sores, ulcers, and redness by damaging the outermost skin cells.[6]

Ideal

properties of herbal sunscreen cream:

- Preferentially absorb light between 280 and 320 nm.
- Resistance to water
- Be resistant to heat, light, and perspiration.
- The user prefers an odourless environment, however minor odours are acceptable.
- Avoid toxicity, irritation, and sensitization.
- Offers long-lasting sun protection.
- Remains stable while use.
- Does not discolour or absorb quickly.
- Maintain neutrality.
- Be quickly soluble in appropriate vehicles.

- Absorb UV rays that cause sunburn. - Stability in sunlight - Complete skin protection - Safety, effectiveness, chemical inertness, low concentration - No irritation, sensitization, or toxicity - No staining Filtering benefits include UVB and UVA radiation protection, antioxidant and reactive oxygen species scavenging, anti-mutagenicity, and anticancer properties.
- Booster effect.[7]

Merits of herbal sunscreen cream

- Helps prevent sunburn and premature ageing
- Provides immediate sun protection upon application.

- Exposure to direct UV radiation extends its lifespan.
- Ideal for persons with heat-sensitive skin (redness).
- Protects against UVA and UVB rays.
- Easily accessible
- Safe and without adverse effects
- Requires no special equipment to prepare
- Cost-effective
- Ingredients are readily available.
- Use renewable resources.[8]

Mechanism of Photo protection

Sunscreen protects skin from harmful UV rays. Sunscreen has been shown to improve UV protection for the skin. The skin's surface scatters and reflects UV radiation in various ways. Mineral-based inorganic sunscreens function similarly in this manner. They provide solar protection for the skin. UV light absorbs heat energy, limiting its damaging effects and penetration into the skin. This is how most organic sunscreens work.

Fig no.1 : Mechanism of Photoprotection

Plan of work

The botanical garden of Shraddha Institute of Pharmacy in Kondala Zambre and local market of Washim, where all the herbal ingredients, including Citrus sinensis (orange peel), Aloevera (Liliaceae), Carrot oil (Daucuscarota), and Turmeric powder (Curcuma Longa), were gathered. Nowadays, practically everyone on the earth uses herbal sunscreen to protect themselves from the damaging effects of UV radiation from sunlight. Because they have a

superior safety profile and fewer adverse effects, herbal remedies are preferred. The creation and assessment of herbal sunscreen creams with anti-inflammatory and anti-UV radiation qualities are the subjects of this study. Plant materials described above were extracted and used to make creams.

Plant material

Herbal sunscreen creams were prepared by using various plant materials such as Citrus sinensis (Orange peel), Aloe vera (Liliaceae), Carrot oil (Daucuscarota), Turmeric (Curcuma Longa).

(A) Aloe vera

- Biological source- dried latex of leaves of it also known as cape aloe .

Fig no. 2 Aloe vera

- Family- liliaceae
- Description Colour- clear to slightly yellow or translucent gold .
- Odour-similar like rotten garlic or onion
- Taste- Bitter
- Chemical constituents- aloe emodin
- Uses- heals burns and clears acne[10]

(B)Turmeric

- Biological source - It consists of dried rhizomes of Curcuma longa
- Family- Zingiberaceae.

Fig no .3 Turmeric

- Description
- Colour - Yellow
- Odour – Aromatic
- Taste – Bitter
- Chief chemical constituents - Curcumin, Curcuminoids
- Uses -Reduce acne, Glowing skin, Lightens skin[11]

(C) Orange

●Biological source: Citrus sinensis commonly known as orange or sweet orange, is a small evergreen tree originally domesticated in subtropical Asia.

Family:Rutaceae

- Description
- Colour-Orange to deep orange outside, depending on the harvesting time.
- Odour-tangy
- Taste-: It tastes so sweet and juicy. Skin is aromatic too.
- Chemical constituents-Limonene, Citral
- Uses-An excellent source of vitamin c.

Fig no .4 Orange

- Chemical constituents-Limonene, Citral

- Uses-An excellent source of vitamin c.[12]
- (D)carrot
- Biological source :Native from Europe and west and central Asia Daucuscarota
 - Family:apiaceae
 - Description
 - Colour: Purple red,orange and white.

Fig no. 5 Carrot

- Odour :Pungent order
- Taste: earthy or bitter
- Chemical constituents: Moisture
- Uses: Anti-Ageing Properties, Skin Brightening, Natural Moisturisation .[13]

Ingredient and their role

Table no .2 list of ingredients and their role

Ingredients	Role of ingredient
Stearic acid	Thickner
Cethyl alcohol	Co emulsifier
Starch	UV protection
Almond oil	Prevents premature aging
Glycerol	Humectant
Aloevera	Prevent Sunburn, Moisturise The Skin
Carrot oil	UV protection
Orange peel powder	Brightening the skin
Methyl parabean	Preservative
Rose water	Fragrance
Triethanolamine	Surface active agent
Carbapol	Gelling Agent
Vit.E	Antioxidant
Turmeric	Anti inflammatory, Anti oxidant
Coconut oil	Moisturizer
Borax	Inhibit microbial growth
Bees wax	Photostability, texture

Instrument

Instruments used for analysis were pH meter , Brookfield viscometer , freezer and UV visible spectrophotometer ,Hot air oven, Hot plate.

Preparation of herbal extract (Tumeric powder)

The dry powder of curcuma longa was packaged individually in plastic bags to avoid contamination. After fully extracting the plant material using ethanol, a maceration process was carried out. Ten grams of each powder were weighed using a digital weighing balance. The powder was then macerated for fifteen hours at room temperature with 150 millilitres of 90% ethanol. Filtering was then used to separate the liquid menstruum from the residue. The ethanolic menstruum was therefore collected and subsequently purified in a round-bottom flask for an hour at a constant temperature. The extracts were extracted for one hour, after which they were transferred to a new container and kept cold for further examination and application.[14]

Fig no.6 Extraction of Tumeric powder

Preparation of orange peel powder

Pick up the fresh oranges from the neighbourhood market in Washim. After cleaning, peel the skin and place the peels in a petri dish. Allow the peel to dry after the hot air oven has warmed up to 75 degrees Celsius for 15 minutes. To make orange peel powder, pulverise the peels.[15]

Fig no .7 Preparation of orange peel powder

Preparation of aloevera gel

Pick fresh carrots from the community market in Washim. After washing, peel the skin, grate the carrots, and transfer them to a petri dish. Allow it to dry for fifteen minutes at 75 degrees Celsius in the hot air oven. After coating a container with coconut oil, place the dried Carrot inside and leave it outside in the sun for 48 hours. After that, filter the oil to get the extract out of it.[16]

**Fig no .8 Formulation of Aloe vera gel
Formulation of herbal sunscreen cream**

Step 1: On a hot plate set at 75 degrees Celsius, the emulsifier (stearic acid) and other oil-soluble ingredients (cethyl alcohol, almond oil, carrot oil, coconut oil, and vitamin E oil) were dissolved in the oil phase.

Fig no.9 Preparation of oil phase

Step 2: Preservatives and other water-soluble components (methylparaben, glycerol, starch, triethanolamine, extract) were dissolved in the aqueous phase and mixed and a sufficient quantity of water was added to the mixture on a hot plate at 75 0

Fig no .10 Preparation of water phase

Step 3: Following the mixing of the two phases, stirring was done continuously until a homogenous result was achieved. Creams were used for additional analysis after being put into a different glass container.

Fig no.11 final Preparation of sunscreen cream

Evaluation of cream:

(1) Physical parameters

- (2)pH Determination
- (3)Determination of Viscosity
- (4)Homogeneity
- (5)Spreadability
- (6)Rancidity
- (7)Washability
- (8)Irritancy test
- (9)After feel
- (10)Determination of SPF

Disclosure of conflict of interest

All authors declare that they have on conflict of interest

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Table no.3 Evaluation of cream

Parameters	Observation
Colour	Whitish yellow
Odour	Rose like
Appearance	Good
pH	6.9 to 7.2
Viscosity	1387 to 1380
Homogeneity	Homogenous
Spreadability	Good
Rancidity	No pink colour
Washability	Good
Irritancy test	Non
SPF value	26

CONCLUSION

The effects of UV radiation on skin damage are numerous and unexpected. Sunburn, inflammatory skin conditions, hyperpigmentation, photoaging, and skin cancer are the outcomes. Cosmetics made of herbs can protect skin from the sun's damaging rays without having any negative or comedogenic effects. The primary focus of this review is the scientific basis for the use of herbal remedies in cosmetics. The active components of herbal extracts have a significant UV-blocking capacity. Herbs are more readily available, environmentally friendly, and harmonic than synthetics.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors are very thankful to the president Dr.Ramkrishan shinde Shraddha institute of pharmacy,washim (India) for providing necessary facilities through principal Dr. Swati Deshmukh to complete this work., And special thanks to the author Vinayak.A. katekar for his creative suggestions, helpful discussion, unfailing advice, constant encouragement during this work

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HOW TO CITE: Vaishnavi P. Bansod, Vinayak A. Katekar and Swati Deshmukh, Dr. Jagdish V. Manwar, Formulation and evaluation of herbal sunscreen cream., *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2024, Vol 2, Issue 8, 2412-2419.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13167007>